

CONSTITUENTS OF *CENTALLA ASIATICA*. PART II.
STRUCTURE OF THE TRITERPENE ACIDS

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The triterpene acids of *Centalla asiatica* from Ceylon have been critically examined and structures assigned to them.

In Part I of this series (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 579), the isolation of three polyhydroxy triterpenic acids—centic acid ($C_{30}H_{48}O_5$), centoic acid ($C_{30}H_{48}O_6$) and centellic acid ($C_{30}H_{48}O_6$)—from the Ceylonese variety of *C. asiatica* has been described. The structures of these acids are now being discussed. The acids have been found to be closely related to the typical triterpenic acids like oleanolic acid. Recently, the structure of asiatic acid, the triterpenic aglycone of the glycoside, asiaticoside, isolated from the Madagascar variety of *C. asiatica*, has been elucidated (Polonsky, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1953, 173). It belongs to the α -amyrin group and is represented by (I).

Since asiatic acid from *C. asiatica* from Madagascar belongs to the α -amyrin group, it has been provisionally assumed that the three acids from the Ceylonese variety of the plant would also belong to the same fundamental group.

Centoic Acid.—With diazomethane it formed a methyl ester ($C_{31}H_{50}O_6$) which could not be hydrolysed by prolonged treatment with acid or alkali, thus revealing the tertiary nature of the carboxyl group. The acid did not show any U.V. absorption and it failed to react with any carbonyl reagent. The absence of any alkoxy group in it was confirmed by Zeisel's method. In alcoholic solution centoic acid and its derivatives developed colour reaction with tetranitromethane, indicating the presence of unsaturation. As in the case of other triterpenes, the double bond was, however, inert and could not be hydrogenated in presence of Adams' catalyst. It reacted with bromine to form a monobromolactone, revealing that, as in the case of many other triterpenic acids, the double bond in this case also was in $\gamma\delta$ -position to the carboxyl group (Winterstein and Hammerle, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1931, 199, 56, 64, 74; Haworth,

Ann. Rep. Chem. Soc., 1939, 338). Dehydrogenation of centoic acid with selenium in the usual way furnished (i) sapotalene or 1:2:7-trimethylnaphthalene, (ii) traces of a phenolic component, (iii) a small amount of a crystalline non-phenolic material having melting and sublimation point very near that of di- or trimethylpicene. These, specially sapotalene, are also the main products obtained by dehydrogenation of oleanolic acid, asiatic acid etc. (Ruzicka *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1932, 15, 1496; 1937, 20, 1155; Boiteau *et al.*, *Nature*, 1949, 163, 258).

Of the six oxygen atoms present in centoic acid, two are accounted for by the carboxyl group. As the acid did not contain any methoxyl, aldehyde or keto group, the other four oxygen atoms could presumably be in the form of hydroxyl groups. On acetylation centoic acid formed a triacetyl derivative ($C_{30}H_{54}O_6$). The methyl ester of this triacetyl derivative showed the presence of an active hydrogen indicating the existence of another hydroxyl group which could not be acetylated and was, presumably, tertiary. In this respect centoic acid differs from asiatic acid (I), all the hydroxyl groups of which are acetylatable.

On heating with copper-bronze (Heywood and Kou, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1125; Tsuda and Kitagawa, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1604) at 350°-380°, centoic acid liberated formaldehyde, which was characterised as its dimedone derivative. This shows that like asiatic acid, centoic acid also possesses at least one primary hydroxyl group.

It has been generally found that if a triterpenic acid possesses an aldehyde or a primary alcoholic group ($-CH_2OH$), it is invariably attached at C_1 with the oxygen atom being actually located on C_{23} (or C_{24}). It is therefore quite reasonable to assume that centoic acid will be no exception, and that the primary alcoholic group, in it is also attached at C_1 , though we have no direct evidence.

Centoic acid consumed one mole of periodate. During this reaction no formaldehyde or acetone was eliminated. Like the parent compound, the resultant scission product also contained 30 carbon atoms ($C_{30}H_{48}O_6$). The glycol linkage in centoic acid therefore does not exist as a side-chain but is a component part of the ring structure itself. This scission product contained at least one aldehyde group as it reduced Fehling's solution and also gave characteristic colour reactions with *o*-dianisidine, benzidine etc. It formed only a monosemicarbazone even when an excess of semicarbazide hydrochloride was used. One of the carbonyl groups in the scission product is therefore inert and must be a hindered, highly substituted keto group as in 2:2:6:6-tetramethylcyclohexanone (II) which has been shown not to form any carbonyl derivatives (Haller and Cornubert, *Compt. rend.*, 1913, 156, 1199). This cannot possibly be an aldehydic group, as all triterpenoid aldehydes do form semicarbazones. It is therefore quite clear that the only resistant hydroxyl group present in centoic acid is a tertiary one, and it forms a part of the glycol linkage. As the scission product is a keto-aldehyde, the other hydroxyl group present in the glycol linkage must be a secondary hydroxyl group. These conditions can be satisfied only by (III) and (IV).

On glycol-cleavage (IV), as distinct from (III), would lead to (VI) with an $\alpha\beta$ -olefinic aldehyde group. Since the scission product obtained from centoic acid did not show any strong ultraviolet absorption specific for an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated carbonylic system, structure (IV) was ruled out. Centoic acid therefore is represented by (III).

Centic Acid.—Analysis and equivalent weight suggest the molecular formula of centic acid as $C_{30}H_{48}O_5$. It contains one oxygen atom less than centoic acid. Like centoic acid it also contains an α -glycol linkage, which from analogy should be located in the same position in the ring system. Centic acid therefore has been represented by (VII)

Centellic Acid.—Details about the molecular formula of centellic acid ($C_{30}H_{48}O_8$) has been described earlier (*loc. cit.*). Like centoic acid it also showed the presence of a primary hydroxyl group (copper-bronze test), an α -glycol linkage, the latter being located in the same position in the ring-system. Centellic acid is, probably, a structural isomer of centoic acid, differing only in the configuration of the glycol linkage. In that case the periodate scission product of the two acids should be identical. But as both the products were amorphous and without having any sharp melting point, a reliable comparison was difficult.

EXPERIMENTAL

Unless otherwise stated, samples were dried to a constant weight at about 100° - 110° /1-2 mm. before examination.

Triacetylcentoic Acid.—The acid (1 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g.), acetic acid (5 c.c.) and acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) were refluxed for 2 to 3 hours. The product was then decomposed in the usual way, extracted with chloroform, purified by precipitating from acetic acid solution with water, and dried. It softened at 160° and formed a glass at 166.69° ; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 5.1$ ($c = 0.834\%$, alcohol). (Found: C, 68.30; H, 8.26; equiv., 633.7. $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$ requires C, 68.55; H, 8.63 per cent. Equiv., 630.80).

Triacetylmethyl ester was prepared by the reaction of the triacetyl derivative and diazomethane in ethereal solution and purified by precipitation from acetic acid solution with water, and dried. It softened at 140° and formed a glass at 160° ; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 7.0$ ($c = 1.142\%$, alcohol). (Found: C, 69.05; H, 9.06; active H, 0.18. $C_{37}H_{66}O_8$ requires C, 68.90; H, 9.76; active H, 0.183 per cent). An identical acetylated methyl ester could also be prepared by acetylating the methyl ester in the usual way with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride.

Monobromolactone of Centoic Acid.—To the acid (0.5 g.), dissolved in methanol (50 c.c.), bromine (0.5 g.), dissolved in methanol (10 c.c.), was added and the mixture set aside for 24 hours. After removal of the solvent the residue was taken up in chloroform and washed successively with bicarbonate, water, and dried. After removal of the chloroform the residue was dissolved in alcohol and precipitated by addition of water. The product indicated a strong Beilstein test for halogen and was insoluble in caustic soda or potash, thus indicating its lactonic nature. (Found: Br, 13.41. $C_{30}H_{47}O_8Br$ requires Br, 13.7 per cent).

Dehydrogenation of Centoic Acid.—The acid (4.5 g.) was intimately mixed with selenium (6 g.) and then heated in a long-necked flask ($2\frac{1}{2}$ ft.) for 48 hours at 350° - 400° . The contents of the flask were then powdered very thoroughly and exhaustively extracted with ether in a Soxhlet apparatus for 24 hours and then with dioxane for another 24 hours. The combined extract after removal of the solvent was once totally distilled at 10^{-3} mm. and then fractionated from a retort at 10^{-3} mm. into four fractions at different bath temperatures: (i) up to 90° , (ii) 90° - 115° , (iii) 115° - 150° and (iv) 150° - 250° .

Fraction (i) contained traces of a phenol and gave a colour reaction with diazonium chloride. The non-phenolic portion and also the fraction (ii) formed a reddish yellow picrate, which after three crystallisations from alcohol melted at 127° , identical with sapotalene picrate, m.p. 128° . Fractions (iii) and (iv) were very small in quantity. After chromatography and micro-vacuum sublimation (bath temperature 250° - $305^{\circ}/10^{-3}$ mm) a product of m.p. 298° was obtained, sublimation temperature and melting point of which compared with those of 1:8-dimethylpicene, m.p. 305 - 306° (corr.) and 1:7:8-trimethylpicene, m.p. 309 - 310° .

Detection of Primary Alcoholic Group.—An intimate mixture of centoic acid (1 g.) and copper-bronze (25 g.) was taken in an adequate apparatus, the side arm of which was dipped in a nearly saturated aqueous solution of dimedone. The flask was heated at 350° - 380° in a metal bath while a slow current of nitrogen was passed through it. The dimedone derivative, which started appearing after 15 minutes, was collected after two hours and crystallised from dilute alcohol; m.p. and mixed m.p. 189° .

Periodate Scission Product of Centoic Acid.—The acid (1.48 g.) was oxidised with periodate (65 c.c., 0.2641 M) following the same procedure as described for the evaluation of the glycol linkage (vide Part I, *loc. cit.*). The scission product was filtered, washed with water and then purified by precipitating with water from alcohol or acetic acid, filtered, washed with water and dried; yield 1.3 g. On a preheated (150°) block it softened at 185° and decomposed at 202° - 205° with frothing; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, $+91.6$ (pyridine, $c = 1.27\%$). (Found: C, 71.45; H, 9.10; equiv., 502.0. $C_{30}H_{48}O_6$ requires C, 71.68; H, 9.22 per cent. Equiv., 502.7).

The product did not show any specific U.V. absorption. The monosemicarbazone of the above scission product was prepared in the usual way. It was finally obtained as a micro-crystalline powder by cooling from a dilute alcoholic solution. In a preheated block it shrank at about 200° and decomposed with frothing at 220° - 225° . (Found: N, 7.36. $C_{21}H_{40}O_6N_2$ requires N, 7.51 per cent).

Centellic Acid.—The acid, as expected, could not be hydrogenated and showed no ultraviolet absorption. The methyl ester was resistant towards acid and alkali.

Acetylation of Centellic Acid.—Acetylation was carried out as in the case of centoic acid. In this case the extent of acetylation depended on the duration of reaction, as indicated by the periodical determination of the equivalent weight: after one hour, approximately 68g; after 2 hours, 700; after 6 hours, 715. Longer heating appeared to induce side reaction. (Found: C, 67.0; H, 8.15; equiv., 710.0. Triacetyl derivative $C_{30}H_{54}O_6$ requires C, 68.54; H, 8.63; tetracetyl derivative $C_{30}H_{58}O_6$ requires C, 67.83; H, 8.39 per cent). For the same sample $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -7.28$ (alcohol, $c = 1.51\%$).

Primary hydroxyl group in centellic acid was detected by employing the same procedure as in the case of centoic acid.

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